

ECOLOGICAL DIVERSITY OF WATERBIRDS FOUND IN UZBEKITAN

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Annotation: The water bodies and wetlands of Uzbekistan provide habitats for a wide variety of waterfowl species. These birds inhabit swamps, lakes, rivers, and artificial reservoirs. More than 100 species of waterfowl have been recorded in Uzbekistan, including herons, cormorants, swans, ducks, geese, and gulls. These birds play a crucial role in the ecosystem by maintaining the ecological balance of aquatic environments. However, their population and distribution are affected by anthropogenic factors, climate change, and habitat degradation. Therefore, ecological research is being conducted in Uzbekistan to protect waterfowl and improve their habitats.

Key words: Waterfowl, ecological diversity, Uzbekistan, water bodies, wetlands, conservation, ecosystem, climate change, anthropogenic impact, habitat.

O‘ZBEKITON HUDUDIDA UCHRAYDIGAN SUV QUSHLARINING EKALOGIK XILMA-XILIGI

Annotatsiya: O‘zbekiston suv havzalari va botqoqlik hududlari xilma-xil suv qushlarining yashash joyi hisoblanadi. Bu hududlarda botqoqlik, ko‘l, daryo va sun‘iy suv havzalarida yashovchi qushlar mavjud. O‘zbekistonda 100 dan ortiq suv qushlari turi qayd etilgan bo‘lib, ular orasida qirg‘ovullar, baliqchi qushlar, oqqushlar, o‘rdaklar, g‘ozlar va chayqalar mavjud. Ushbu qushlar ekotizimning muhim qismi bo‘lib, suv muhitining barqarorligini saqlashga yordam beradi. Ularning soni va tarqalishiga antropogen omillar, iqlim o‘zgarishi va tabiiy muhitning degradatsiyasi ta‘sir ko‘rsatadi. Shu sababli, O‘zbekistonda suv qushlarini muhofaza qilish va ularning yashash muhitini yaxshilash bo‘yicha ekologik tadqiqotlar olib borilmoqda.

Kalit so‘zlar: Suv qushlari, ekologik xilma-xillik, O‘zbekiston, suv havzalari, botqoqlik, muhofaza, ekotizim, iqlim o‘zgarishi, antropogen ta‘sir, yashash muhiti.

Introduction: Although Uzbekistan is located in the arid region of Central Asia, it is home to a variety of aquatic ecosystems. The country's rivers, lakes, reservoirs, and wetlands support biodiversity. These areas are particularly important habitats for waterfowl. Waterfowl play an important role in maintaining ecological balance, ensuring the stability of the food chain, and as bioindicators. This article discusses the waterfowl found in Uzbekistan and their ecological diversity.

Main part: Birds that live in and regularly occur in water bodies in Uzbekistan are adapted to different ecosystems. They can be divided into the following categories. Resident water birds, This category includes birds that live permanently in the territory of Uzbekistan. They are found in local water bodies all year round. Swan (*Cygnus olor*), Duck species (*Anas spp.*), Coot (*Fulica atra*), Greater and lesser grebes (*Podiceps spp.*) Migratory water birds There are also birds that migrate through Uzbekistan in spring and autumn. The most prominent among them are:

Grey Goose (*Anser anser*), White-tailed Eagle (*Haliaeetus albicilla*), Red-legged Gull (*Larus ridibundus*), White and Grey Egret (*Egretta garzetta*, *Ardea cinerea*) Wintering Waterfowl During the cold season, the villages of Northern Europe and Siberia temporarily winter in Uzbekistan: Mute Swan (*Cygnus cygnus*), Shearwater Goose (*Tadorna ferruginea*), The role of waterfowl in the ecosystem. Waterfowl are not only part of biodiversity, but also organisms that provide ecosystem services.

Their main ecological functions are: An important link in the food chain - they regulate populations by feeding on aquatic insects, fish and algae. Hygiene of wetlands and water bodies - they maintain the ecological balance of water by consuming decaying plants. As a bioindicator - they are considered indicators of the state of the environment, as they react sensitively to water pollution or a decrease in food sources. Threats and protective measures Waterfowl in Uzbekistan are under threat due to the following factors: Drying of water bodies - water resources are decreasing as a result of climate change and anthropogenic factors. Hunting and poaching - some wild bird species are being illegally hunted. Toxic substances and chemical pollution - pesticides used in agriculture and industrial waste pose a serious threat to waterfowl. To reduce these threats, the following measures must be taken: Expanding protected areas and ensuring safe migration routes for birds. Protective measures. In recent years, a number of works have been carried out in Uzbekistan to protect waterfowl:

The network of reserves and national parks is being expanded: areas such as the Aral Sea Biosphere Reserve, Dengizkul, and Todakul. Work within the framework of the Ramsar Convention: Uzbekistan has been a member of the Ramsar Convention since 2001 and has undertaken to protect wetlands. Scientific

monitoring and research: Regular monitoring of waterfowl populations, identification of their migration routes, introduction of biomonitoring methods. Development of ecotourism and environmental education: Ecological tourist routes are being organized to observe waterfowl. Strengthening legislation and combating poaching. Protection of water resources and taking measures against pollution.

Conclusion: The ecological diversity of waterfowl in Uzbekistan is of great importance for the natural wealth and ecological stability of the country. Waterfowl not only enrich biodiversity, but also serve as an important indicator of the ecological state of water bodies. At a time when factors such as the Aral Sea tragedy, improper management of water resources, pollution and climate change pose a serious threat to the habitat of waterfowl, their protection and stabilization of their numbers are one of the urgent tasks of today.

There is an opportunity to preserve waterfowl by expanding state-protected areas, complying with international environmental conventions, conducting scientific observations and increasing the ecological culture of the population. In particular, attracting the public through ecotourism and environmental education is an important factor in encouraging people to protect nature. Therefore, preserving the ecological diversity of waterfowl in Uzbekistan is not only about taking protective measures, but also about ensuring the sustainable development of natural ecosystems, leaving a healthy and rich nature as a legacy for future generations. The responsible attitude of each of us to nature creates the basis for the continuation of the life of waterfowl.

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